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USING GIS TECHNOLOGY IN SOIL-ECOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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***Аннотация.** В статье представлен опыт применения геоинформационных систем для оценки концентраций различных потенциально токсичных поллютантов на фоновых территориях. Рассмотрены результаты исследований на примере гетерогенных (почвы) объектов окружающей среды.*

***Annotation.** The article presents the experience of using geo-information systems to assess the concentrations of various potentially toxic pollutants in background areas. The results of the research on the example of heterogeneous environmental objects (soils) are considered.*

***Key words:** soil, monitoring, potentially toxic substances, heavy metals, hydrocarbons.*

Introduction. The global nature of environmental problems associated with transboundary movement of pollutants, as well as regional and local sources of pollution, require new approaches to assess the specific environmental situation in ecosystems. The issues of monitoring the ecological status of soils and studying the levels of a wide range of potentially toxic substances (PTSs) in different environments are becoming increasingly important (Ishkova et al., 2012; Haghhighizadeh et al., 2024).

In modern conditions of environmental pollution, soils are the main repository of PTSs – heavy metals (HMs) and hydrocarbons (HCs) – and the biogeochemical barrier for their transport to plants, animals and the human body (Beznosikov, Lodygin, 2018; Liu et al., 2023). At the same time, the determination of regional background concentrations of PTSs in soils should serve as a “reference point” for the determination of environmental exposure (Nevedrov et al., 2018). In particular, when assessing soil contamination with PM, existing regulations require the determination of the excess of the mass fraction of this pollutant over the maximum permissible concentration (MPC). In the Russian Federation, MPCs are permitted for HMs, but the list is limited (SanPiN 1.2.3685-21, 2022). In a number of cases, the developed standards for some HMs turned out to be logically inconsistent with their background levels in soils. In our opinion, it is impossible to use such MPCs as the upper limit of the background content of HMs is sometimes higher than the MPCs. At present, in the absence of MPCs for HMs, existing regulatory documents recommend the use of regional background levels when assessing soil contamination.

There is practically no modern regulatory framework for the content of petroleum HCs in soils in the Russian Federation. The only domestic standard for the content of petroleum products in soils is the MPC of petrol – 0.1 mg/kg. On the territory of the Komi Republic there are norms for the permissible residual

content of oil and products of its transformation in soils after reclamation and other rehabilitation works. Analysis of the few data on norms of background content of HCs in soils shows that their regulation applies only to certain areas of the region (Lodygin et al., 2025). Therefore, the assessment of the natural background of HCs is an urgent task for the whole territory of the Republic of Komi, the solution of which will allow to objectively determine soil contamination, which will make it possible to impose restrictions on both industrial and agricultural technologies.

As a result, the available information on the instructional and methodological literature regulating the permissible PTSs loads on soils allows to state that the existing norms in the field of anthropogenic loads are not differentiated by natural-climatic zones and landscape-geochemical conditions of the region, so they cannot be used in a particular area when assessing soil pollution.

The aim of the work is to assess the regional background of HMs and HCs in soils of the Komi Republic, taking into account the landscape-geochemical and natural-climatic features of the territories.

Materials and Methods. The study focused on soils of the arctic and subarctic regions of the Republic of Komi. Soil samples were collected from organogenic and mineral horizons of the main soil types. The state soil map of the Komi Republic (M 1:1000000) was digitised for the landscape-geochemical assessment of the ecological condition of the soil cover (Fig. 1).

A systematic list of soils in the study areas was compiled on the basis of the soil map. The areas were calculated, and the points of laying reference transects and collecting mixed samples of the main soil types and subtypes were determined. The route method was used for soil sampling to take into account the regularities of soil cover formation in landscapes, from watersheds (automorphic soils) to geochemically subordinate landscapes (depressions, hydromorphic soils).

The analyses were performed in the Ecoanalytical Laboratory of the Institute of Biology (Syktyvkar, Russia), accredited in the system of accreditation of analytical laboratories (centers) of Rosstandart of Russia.

The determination of the content of acid-soluble forms of HMs (Cu, Pb, Zn, Ni, Cd and Mn) in soils was conducted in accordance with a metrologically certified method, which is based on the determination of metal ions on an inductively coupled argon plasma atomic emission spectrometer (Spectro Ciros, Germany). The method involves the treatment of soil samples with a mixture of 70% HNO₃ and 33% H₂O₂ in a microwave-accelerated reaction system MARS 5 (CEM, USA) (PND F 16.1:2.3:3.11-98, 2005).

Figure 1. Soil map of the Komi Republic

The concentration of HCs in soil samples was determined by the fluorescence intensity values of the hexane extract measured on the Fluorat-02-03M liquid analyser (Lumex, Russia). The technique is based on extraction of oil from the soil sample with chloroform, evaporation of the extract, dissolution of the dry extract in hexane and purification of the resulting solution on an Al₂O₃-column. The analyzer was calibrated using an optical light filter with a wavelength (transmission maximum) of 265 nm in the excitation channel and a light filter with a transmission maximum of 320 nm in the registration channel. The government

standard sample of 1 mg/ml of petrochemical substances dissolved in hexane was used as a reference.

Results and Discussion. The results of the studies have shown that in the soils of the background landscapes of the Komi Republic the mass fractions of HMs and HCs follow or are close to the normal distribution law. They are characterized by positive asymmetry, which in most cases indicates that the largest number of variations falls on values smaller than the arithmetic mean. The range of background variations of HM and HC contents with a significance level of 0.5 is narrow for soils of flat landscapes - swamp-podzol, bog, tundra surface-gley and gley-podzol soils. This is due to the uniformity of the soil-forming rocks, the close granulometric composition of the soils on clayey soils and uniform migration patterns across the landscape. Similar patterns of HM and HC mass fractions were observed in soils formed on ancient alluvial and water-glacial sandy sediments (illuvial-humus podzols) and on poorly drained plain watersheds of uvals, fluvio-glacial terraces covered with sandy sediments (peaty-podzolic illuvial-humus soils), but their absolute content in these soils is lower than in soils formed on loamy soil-forming rocks. In the mountainous part, the accumulation of HM and HC in the soils and their mass fractions of the arithmetic averages vary, but do not differ in a statistically reliable way.

It is shown that the accumulation of PTPs occurs mainly in organic horizons and in insignificant amounts in illuvial horizons. Organic horizons serve as a geochemical barrier for elements and, as a result, their accumulation (concentration) in humus-accumulating horizons (litter) occurs in almost all soils studied (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Distribution maps of PTPs in soils of the Komi Republic: A – nickel, B – copper, C – zinc, D – cadmium, E – lead and F – hydrocarbons.

The "geochemical fate" of HMs and HCs is determined by the landscape features of the territory (Soil Atlas..., 2010). The Komi Republic has developed landscapes (landscape-ecological conditions) with different topography, granulometric composition of soil-forming rocks, etc., which determine the peculiarities of accumulation and migration of HMs, HCs and radionuclides. The most widespread landscapes in the Komi Republic are moraine (weakly buried) and cover (dusty) poorly drained plains represented by gentle hill chains and inter-hill depressions. These areas are characterized by swampy-podzol soils, which develop in the central part of watersheds and on the periphery of bogs, and peaty-boggy soils of upper bogs in intervalley depressions (Lodygin, 2020). These soils are over-watered, their geochemical subordination determines lateral runoff and accumulative character by accumulation of HM and HC nuclides in organic horizons. In the range of automorphic soils, the following soils are restricted to the drained landscapes of riverine uplands: gley-podzol soils in the extreme northern and northern taiga, typical podzol soils in the middle taiga, sod-podzol soils in the southern taiga subzone, which are characterized by moderate migration of elements with their predominant accumulation in coarse humus accumulative and low thickness sod horizons (Shamrikova et al., 2011).

In the watersheds, soil-forming rocks with two components predominate: fluvioglacial sandy loams and sands underlain by moraine loams (swamp-podzol-illuvial-humus soils), in the old alluvial pig terraces: In the central taiga subzone, ferruginous podzols are distinguished, in the northern taiga subzone – illuvial-humus-ferruginous podzols: the main amount of pollutants is concentrated in thin, poorly developed litter, poorly decomposed wet peaty (peaty), mossy peaty litter, but migration processes are well expressed in them. Floodplain landscapes are characterized by relatively active migration of natural and artificial radionuclides of HMs and HCs from soils (alluvial soils: alluvial stratified, alluvial soddy and alluvial soddy-perennial), floodplain soils are characterized by relatively uniform profile distribution of pollutants.

Summary and Suggestions. The results of the geochemical assessment of the ecological condition of soils allowed to establish norms of the regional background of HMs and HCs in soils of Komi Republic. On the basis of the obtained data set, using GIS technologies (ArcView GIS 3.2a), a database and map schemes of spatial, background distribution of elements (substances) in soils were created and the Order of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environmental Protection of the Komi Republic dated 25 November 2009 no. 529 "On establishment of norms of background content of chemical elements and hydrocarbons in soils of the Komi Republic" was issued. This order is systematically supplemented (corrected) with new data. At present, the results of the conducted research are regional norms, which are the basis for systematic monitoring studies and comprehensive assessment of the environmental situation of the territory in areas of possible soil contamination. The obtained norms are used in the preparation of engineering and environmental assessments of areas proposed for new development of various sectors.

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ЦИФРОВАЯ КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ЗЕМЕЛЬ В СИСТЕМЕ ЗЕМЛЕУСТРОИТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЯ

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***Аннотация.** В работе рассмотрены вопросы комплексной оценки земель на примере южной лесостепи Окско-Донской низменности. Показан потенциал принятия землеустроительных решений на основе совместного применения реестров земель и сортов, регистра агротехнологий для повышения экономической эффективности и экологической устойчивости агроландшафта.*

***Ключевые слова:** агроэкологическая оценка, группы земель, реестр земель, реестр агротехнологий, чернозёмы.*

***Annotation.** The article examines the issues of integrative land assessment using the example of the southern forest-steppe of the Oka-Don Lowland. It shows the potential for land management decisions based on the joint use of land types, variety and agricultural technologies register improve the economic efficiency and environmental sustainability of the agricultural landscape.*

***Keywords:** agroecological assessment, land groups, land registry, register of agrotechnologies, chernozems.*

Введение и анализ литературы по теме. В условиях достаточно высокого природного потенциала плодородия земель черноземной зоны Восточно-Европейской равнины сохраняется низкая эффективность растениеводства, сопровождающаяся деградацией почв и земель (Анализ..., 2016; Кирюшин, 2019; Иванов и др., 2021). Частично это связано с тем, что достижения и рекомендации научных учреждений слабо интегрируются в научно-инновационные системы и не дифференцированы в должной мере с учетом почвенно-ландшафтных условий страны. Преодоление этой проблемы видится в создании цифровых платформ управления агропромышленным комплексом на разных уровнях его организации (Кирюшин, 2022) за счет использования методологии территориальной оптимизации сельскохозяйственного землепользования на основе согласования комплексной оценки агропроизводственного потенциала земель, экологических требований культур и региональных возможностей агротехнологий различного уровня интенсивности (Кирюшин, 2020). Исходную позицию составляет формализация оценочных требований в виде реестра биологических особенностей сортов сельскохозяйственных культур и регистра агротехнологий. В соответствии с этими требованиями последовательно разрабатывается агроэкологическая, агрономическая и экономическая оценка видов земель по их агроэкологическим группам в пределах провинций природно-сельскохозяйственных зон.